

beginning at 35 days after transplanting. The disease incidence was recorded at the heading stage as percentage of infected tillers, based on random

observations of all the tillers in 20 hills/plot.

All fungicides reduced the disease incidence significantly (see table). The

treatment thiram + edifenphos was most effective, followed by PCNB + edifenphos. Among foliar fungicides, carbendazim performed best. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Notes on *Athetis pectinicornis*, a pest of water lettuce and water hyacinth in Bangladesh

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The free-floating water lettuce *Pistia stratiotes* L. is a small aquatic perennial with a tuft of long, very fibrous roots. In certain situations it seriously interferes with the rice crop and is a preferred host

of several species of mosquitoes, which in turn serve as principal vectors of malaria, encephalomyelitis, and rural filariasis.

Water hyacinth *Eichhornia crassipes* (Mart.) Solms seriously interferes with irrigation and navigation in many areas by blocking the canals with its diverse growth. It also impedes water flow in rivers, canals, and waterways. In Bangladesh, dhaincha *Sesbania cannabina* Pers. is sometimes cultivated on the border of rice fields to check the weed's entrance into the field.

In April and May 1978, caterpillars of *Athetis pectinicornis* Hamp. (Noctuidae; Lepidoptera) were found feeding on the leaves of these two weeds in several places in Dacca city. The insect appears to be a natural control agent of water lettuce and water hyacinth, and deserves the attention of entomologists and weed management specialists.

The pest species was identified by Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, U.K. ■

Evaluation of depth and effective zone of placement of carbofuran for brown planthopper control

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Carbofuran at 2.0 kg a.i./ha was placed in capsules, which were set near root zones of potted plants at depths of 1.25, 2.50, 3.75, and 5.00 cm from the soil surface. Ten adult brown planthoppers were released onto the plants at 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 days after treatment. Mortality was recorded 24 hours after insect release.

Regardless of placement depth, 80 to 100% mortality was recorded.

The effective zone for insecticide placement was studied in a 90- × 90-cm iron tray, with plants spaced at 20 × 20 cm. Carbofuran at 2.0 kg a.i./ha was used. The relative position of hills, interspacing between hills, and the exact placement points of insecticide in the root zone are shown in the figure. The plants were removed 5 days after application.

Root portions of the plants were wrapped with wet cotton, covered with polyethylene, and kept in glass chimneys. Both ends of the chimneys were tied with

Representation of the relative position of rice hills and actual points of insecticide placement in the root zone. • = plant hill, x = insecticide placement.

fine muslin. BPH adults were confined on the plants and mortality was recorded 48 hours later.

The insecticide did not move laterally from its placement point in the root zone. Bioassay tests of plants failed to show insecticide even after 48 hours of exposure of BPH adults.

Carbofuran at 2.0 kg a.i./ha (calculated on the basis of the diameter of the tray) was placed as a lump in the center of

4 hills spaced 10 × 10 cm in a 90- × 90-cm iron tray. Insect releases and observations were the same as in the previous experiment.

When the total amount of insecticide required to treat 1 m² was centrally placed as 1 lump, it had no effect on the next plants, 10 cm from the central 4 hills. That showed that the insecticide did not move laterally from its placement point. ■